

Socio Emotional Competence and Literacy Progression Among Learners in Public Elementary Schools

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Abstract. The primary objective of this study was to examine the socio-emotional competence and literacy progression of learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. A non-experimental, quantitative design employing descriptive and correlational techniques was used to gather data from a representative sample. Findings revealed that overall socio-emotional competence was extensive, with learners frequently demonstrating strong emotional regulation and social initiation. However, empathy and conflict resolution were moderately extensive, suggesting specific areas for further development. Literacy progression was also extensive, particularly in reading accuracy, text comprehension, and writing clarity, while vocabulary usage was moderately extensive. A significant positive relationship was identified between overall socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among the learners. Further analysis revealed that emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution had a notable influence on literacy outcomes, whereas social initiation did not show a significant impact. These results imply that integrating targeted socio-emotional learning with literacy instruction could enhance academic achievement. Consequently, the study offers important implications for educational policymakers and practitioners aiming to develop holistic interventions that support learner development.

KEY WORDS

1. Socio-emotional competence 2. literacy progression 3. elementary education 4. educational interventions 5. Sulop District, Davao del Sur

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1. Introduction

The decline in literacy levels among learners in public elementary schools has raised serious concerns among educators, parents, and policymakers. Many students struggle with basic reading comprehension and writing skills, which affect their overall academic performance. Socio-emotional competence, encompassing self-awareness, empathy, and relationship-building, has been recognized as a crucial factor that influences how effectively learners engage with academic tasks. Investigating the extent to which socio-emotional competence supports literacy progression among elementary school learners is therefore crucial. This study aims to provide insights into how strengthening socio-emotional skills can address the literacy challenges faced by these learners, thus leading to improved academic outcomes. In the United States, the decline in literacy among learners has been a growing con-

cern due to various social and economic factors. According to Baron and Mangen (2021), many students have limited access to quality reading materials and supportive home environments that promote literacy. Sun et al. (2023) also emphasized the rise in digital distractions, which compete with traditional reading habits and reduce consistent practice in reading and writing. Additionally, some schools face large class sizes, making it difficult for teachers to provide individualized attention. Hence, developing comprehensive literacy programs that address these issues has become a pressing priority for educators and policymakers. In Arab countries, the decline in literacy is often attributed to traditional teaching methods that prioritize rote memorization over critical thinking. Al-mazroui and Albloushi (2024) noted that students are not encouraged to engage deeply with reading materials, resulting in shallow comprehension and a low interest in reading. Meanwhile, Al-Bataineh (2021) noted a shortage of age-appropriate Arabic reading resources, which further complicates efforts to improve literacy. Moreover, many teachers were not fully equipped with strategies to promote active learning in the classroom. Thus, educators in Arab countries are calling for reforms that integrate modern teaching approaches and provide more diverse reading materials for learners. Across Asia, the decline in literacy was often linked to overcrowded classrooms and high-stakes exams that prioritize memorization over genuine comprehension. Le Nestour, Moscoviz, and Sandefur (2022) argued that when teachers must manage large numbers of students, they have less time to support individuals struggling with reading. Similarly, Salihu (2020) revealed that too much focus on test preparation can leave little room for activities that foster reading comprehension and critical thinking. Also, limited resources in rural areas can restrict access to quality reading materials. Therefore, Asian education systems are encouraged

to implement policies that reduce class sizes and balance test preparation with strategies that nurture students' reading skills. In the Philippines, literacy challenges persist, particularly in regions where educational resources are scarce. Ocampo and Buenviaje (2024) discussed how inadequate funding and limited teacher training contribute to learners' reading difficulties. Magno (2022) observed that the linguistic diversity in the country can also complicate language instruction, leading to confusion and lower motivation to read in English and Filipino. Moreover, many schools lack access to technology and modernized reading materials, hindering students' exposure to engaging content. As a result, more robust teacher development programs and improved distribution of educational materials are necessary to address the nation's literacy challenges. Focusing on Davao del Sur, the decline in literacy is further intensified by a mix of economic constraints and limited community involvement in education. Many families in rural areas struggle to provide consistent reading support at home due to livelihood concerns. Additionally, some schools in remote barangays face challenges with insufficient instructional materials and outdated textbooks, making it difficult for learners to develop strong reading skills. The lack of collaboration between schools and local leaders can also limit the reach of literacy initiatives. Consequently, stakeholders in Davao del Sur are exploring partnerships with government and non-government agencies to enhance literacy programs and ensure that learning resources are both accessible and culturally relevant. Despite the increasing awareness of the significant role socio-emotional competence plays in academic success, there remains a substantial research gap in understanding how these skills specifically impact literacy progression among elementary learners in rural areas such as Sulop District, Davao del Sur. Most existing studies focus on urban or suburban settings and often overlook the unique challenges and

environmental factors of rural districts. Furthermore, there is limited quantitative data that isolates socio-emotional competencies as a determinant factor in literacy outcomes, leaving a critical gap in effective, evidence-based educational strategies tailored for these communities. This lack of targeted research has hindered the development of programs that could address both the emotional and cognitive needs of students in these less-represented areas. The urgency to conduct this study in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, stems from the pressing need to improve educational outcomes in a region where resources are scarce and literacy rates are below the national average. Understanding the relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression can provide essential insights into how educators and policymakers can better support these learners. By conducting a quantitative analysis, the study aims to produce concrete, actionable data that can lead to the implementation of tailored interventions designed to foster both emotional well-being and academic proficiency. Such research is crucial not only for improving literacy rates but also for ensuring that students develop the necessary skills to succeed in all areas of their education.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Socio-Emotional Competence*—Socio-emotional competence refers to learners' ability to understand, manage, and express emotions, form positive relationships, and handle social challenges effectively (Pérez Muneton, 2023; Knigge et al., 2019). Students with stronger socio-emotional skills show better academic performance, adaptability, and school adjustment. Moderate competence, however, may cause inconsistent emotional regulation and social interaction (Rocha et al., 2024). Integrating SEL programs into the curriculum enhances emotional awareness, peer relationships, and classroom engagement (Portela-Pino et al., 2021).

Socio-emotional competence varies by environment and academic achievement. Urban students and high achievers tend to exhibit stronger emotional control (Bhat, 2023). Structured training also boosts emotional awareness and communication among educators (Freeman, 2024). Furthermore, socio-emotional competence supports literacy by fostering empathy, persistence, and collaboration—skills essential for reading comprehension and interactive learning (Turner-Moore, 2022; Batini et al., 2021; Aleksić et al., 2019).

1.1.2. *Emotional Regulation*—Emotional regulation allows students to manage and respond appropriately to emotions, influencing both academic success and well-being (Pérez Bahamon Muneton, 2023). Children with strong emotional regulation display better behavior and academic focus (Schlesier et al., 2019). Effective emotional control supports perseverance in subjects like mathematics (Haun, 2020) and enhances confidence (Hanin et al., 2021). Cognitive regulation also reduces anxiety and procrastination, improving focus and motivation (Rezaei Zebardast, 2021).

Emotional regulation directly benefits literacy development. Students who manage emotions effectively perform better in reading comprehension and maintain engagement (Burney, 2022; Yu et al., 2023). Thus, emotional regulation is a foundational skill linking emotional balance with academic growth.

1.1.3. *Empathy*—Empathy enables learners to understand and share others' emotions, strengthening relationships and social interactions (Pérez Bahamon Muneton, 2023). Empathetic students are more cooperative and emotionally intelligent (Compton Lindner, 2025). However, moderate empathy may lead to inconsistent understanding of social cues, creating classroom misunderstandings (Zaky, 2024; Guan et al., 2024). Integrating empathy-based activities enhances relationships, collaboration, and inclusivity (Ortega-Ochoa et al., 2024;

Zhang, 2022).

Empathy also improves literacy, allowing students to connect deeply with texts and understand character motivations (Howard, 2024; Patel, 2023). Developing empathy thus supports both interpersonal and cognitive aspects of learning.

1.1.4. Social Initiation—Social initiation—confidence to start interactions—fosters friendships, emotional security, and group collaboration (Pérez Bahamon Muneton, 2023; Aal Ismail et al., 2022). Highly socially competent students energize class participation and teamwork (Kaseke Luvalo, 2025; McDuffie, 2021). They also promote inclusion, bridging peer groups and strengthening classroom harmony (Monfaredi, 2023; Estaji Shojakhanlou, 2023).

Strong social initiation enhances literacy by encouraging participation in reading groups and peer discussions, improving vocabulary and comprehension (Tuelo Munsaka, 2021; Mohammadzaheri et al., 2021).

1.1.5. Conflict Resolution—Conflict resolution involves negotiating and resolving disagreements constructively (Pérez Bahamon Muneton, 2023). It maintains positive classroom environments and builds teamwork (Johnson Johnson, 2019). Students with moderate skills may struggle occasionally but benefit from training and peer mediation programs (Morozova et al., 2022; Hatun Serin, 2021). Real-life conflicts also serve as teachable moments that enhance emotional intelligence (Kapshuk Alt, 2022; Ramirez, 2019).

Conflict resolution supports literacy development by improving participation in group discussions and reducing social disruptions during reading activities (Camacho Ortiz, 2020; Goldschmidt Pedro, 2019).

1.1.6. Literacy Progression of Students—Literacy progression encompasses the continuous development of reading, writing, and comprehension skills critical for lifelong learning

(Kanniainen et al., 2019; Cameron et al., 2020). High literacy levels enhance academic success and critical thinking (Abbas et al., 2019; Kedra Žakevičiūtė, 2019). Combined reading methods—timed, repeated, and extensive reading—promote fluency and comprehension (Milliner, 2021). Guided discovery learning and targeted assessments also strengthen literacy outcomes (Warlinda et al., 2022; Lam, 2019).

1.1.7. Reading Accuracy—Reading accuracy—the ability to read words correctly—underpins fluency and comprehension (Kanniainen et al., 2019). Balanced phonics and oral reading strategies moderately improve accuracy and understanding (Clinton, 2019; Torgerson et al., 2019; Yildiz et al., 2019).

1.1.8. Text Comprehension—Comprehension allows students to interpret meaning and engage critically with texts (Säuberli, 2021). Learners with moderate comprehension often grasp literal meanings but struggle with inference and evaluation (Bogaerds-Hazenbergh et al., 2021). Strategies like concept mapping and text-based questioning deepen comprehension (Shanniyah, 2019; Fitria, 2019).

1.1.9. Writing Clarity and Organization—Writing clarity involves structuring ideas coherently and using precise language (Eck, 2022). Well-organized writing promotes deeper thinking and academic performance (Li Huang, 2022; Kelly Gaytan, 2020). Cohesive writing enhances readability and comprehension (Shin Epp, 2023; Hornby, 2024).

1.1.10. Vocabulary Usage—Vocabulary breadth enables precise communication and comprehension (Ketola, 2019). Limited vocabulary constrains complex thinking and content understanding (Lee et al., 2019). Pre-teaching key terms and using CLIL or interactive vocabulary strategies improve academic language proficiency (Maamuujav, 2021; Olsson, 2021; Al-Sharah et al., 2021).

1.2. Synthesis—Socio-emotional competence, which encompasses skills such as em-

pathy, self-regulation, and cooperation, plays a vital role in improving the educational outcomes of learners. Studies have consistently demonstrated that students who exhibit higher levels of these competencies tend to perform better academically, as they are better equipped to handle stress, interact positively with peers and teachers, and adapt to the demands of the school environment. Also, literature suggests that socio-emotional skills specifically aid in literacy development by improving students' ability to understand and interpret complex texts, engage in meaningful discussions, and express their thoughts coherently in writing. These skills foster a positive attitude towards learning, increase students' engagement in classroom activities, and enhance their motivation to read and write, all of which are fundamental for literacy progression. However, despite the established importance of socio-emotional competence in promoting literacy, a noticeable gap existed in research specifically targeting rural educational settings. Rural schools often face unique challenges such as limited resources, fewer qualified teachers, and isolation from mainstream educational support, which can impact the implementation and effectiveness of programs aimed at developing these competencies. More so, rural learners may experience different socio-cultural dynamics that influence the development of their socio-emotional skills differently compared to their urban counterparts. Therefore, exploring the relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression in a rural setting is crucial. It could provide valuable insights into tailoring educational interventions that address the specific needs and constraints of rural learners, ensuring that these programs are both relevant and practical. Conducting a study in a rural context, such as in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, is therefore essential. It not only fills a significant research gap but also contributes to a more equitable distribution of educational research efforts, which

predominantly focus on urban and suburban settings. By investigating how socio-emotional competence influences literacy among rural students, educators and policymakers can develop targeted strategies that genuinely resonate with and benefit these communities. Such research can lead to the creation of tailored teaching methods that integrate socio-emotional learning with literacy instruction, potentially transforming educational practices to better support all learners, regardless of their geographic location. Ultimately, this focus on rural education could significantly contribute to reducing educational disparities and promoting literacy development across diverse settings.

1.3. *Theoretical/Conceptual Framework*—

This study was grounded in Emotional Intelligence Theory, as proposed by Goleman (1995). Emotional Intelligence Theory focuses on the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions as well as the emotions of others. This theory emphasizes that emotional skills are essential for personal and academic success. This theory is highly relevant to the study as it highlights how students' abilities to manage their emotions can impact their learning, particularly in literacy. By developing emotional intelligence, learners can create a more positive and focused environment for reading and comprehension. Additionally, emotional skills like empathy and self-regulation support cooperative learning, which can enhance literacy progression. Implementing strategies based on Emotional Intelligence Theory can help educators foster a supportive classroom atmosphere that promotes better reading skills among learners in Sulop District. This alignment ensures that socio-emotional competence directly contributes to improved literacy outcomes. In support, Self-Determination Theory, proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985), posits that fulfilling the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness enhances motivation and psychological well-being. This theory is suit-

able for the study because it explores how motivation affects literacy progression among students. By fostering intrinsic motivation through the development of socio-emotional competencies, students are more likely to engage actively with reading materials. Additionally, supporting students' needs for autonomy and competence can lead to a more motivated and confident approach to learning the English language. Applying Self-Determination Theory helps educators create learning environments that enhance students' motivation, thereby improving their literacy skills and overall academic performance in Sulop District. This approach ensures that socio-emotional competence contributes effectively to literacy development. Lastly, Ecological Systems Theory, as proposed by Bronfenbrenner (1979), describes how a child's development is influenced by various environmental systems, ranging from immediate settings such as family and school to broader societal factors. Urie Bronfenbrenner introduced this theory in 1979, highlighting the complex interactions between a child and their environment. This theory is appropriate for the study as it considers the various environmental factors that affect socio-emotional competence and literacy progression. Understanding how different layers of the environment in Sulop District influence students' emotional and academic development helps identify key areas for intervention. Additionally, Bronfenbrenner's framework supports the examination of how family, school,

and community interactions contribute to literacy outcomes. Using this theory enables the researcher to adopt a holistic approach to improving literacy by enhancing socio-emotional skills, thereby addressing both individual and contextual factors. This study was composed of two variables, as shown in Figure 1. The independent variable is socio-emotional competence, which refers to the ability to understand, manage, and express the social and emotional aspects of one's life effectively. The measures of socio-emotional competence are emotional regulation or the student's ability to manage and respond to an emotional experience in an appropriate manner; empathy or the ability to understand and share the feelings, thoughts, and experiences of another person from their perspective; social initiation or the ability to start interactions or engage with others in social situations, such as beginning a conversation, asking questions, or joining group activities; and conflict resolution or the ability to negotiate and constructively resolve disagreements. The dependent variable is literacy progression or the ongoing development and enhancement of skills necessary to decode, comprehend, and produce both spoken and written language. The indicators of literacy progression are reading accuracy, or the ability to pronounce words and read text without errors, and text comprehension, or the ability to understand and interpret the meaning behind it.

Words and phrases within a context; writing clarity and organization, or the ability to express thoughts in a clear, logical, and coherent manner through writing; and vocabulary usage, or the ability and frequency with which students use a diverse and appropriate vocabulary in both spoken and written forms.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study was set to explore the socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. Hence, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of socio-emotional competence of learners in terms of:
 - (1) emotional regulation;

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

- (2) empathy;
 - (3) social initiation; and
 - (4) Conflict Resolution?
- (2) What is the extent of literacy progression among learners in terms of:
- (1) reading accuracy;
 - (2) text comprehension;
 - (3) writing clarity and organization; and
 - (4) Vocabulary Usage?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools?
- (4) Which domains of socio-emotional competence significantly influence the literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools?

1.5. *Hypotheses*—The following hypotheses will be tested at the 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools. H02: None of the domains of socio-emotional competence significantly influences the literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Socio Emotional Competence. It was defined conceptually as the individual’s ability to understand, manage,

and express the social and emotional aspects of their lives effectively. In this study, the second independent variable was described in terms of the following indicators: emotional regulation, empathy, social initiation, and conflict resolution. Literacy Progression. It was defined conceptually as the ongoing development and enhancement of skills necessary to decode, comprehend, and produce both spoken and written language. In this study, the dependent variable was described in terms of reading accuracy, text comprehension, writing clarity and organization, and vocabulary usage.

2. Methodology

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the research design, including details on the research respondents, ethical considerations, research instruments, and procedural steps. It also outlines the methods for data collection and analysis, ensuring a clear framework for the study.

2.1. Research Design—In the context of this study, the researcher had opted for a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. A quantitative research design involved the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It aimed to quantify relationships, test hypotheses, and generate numerical data that could be transformed into usable statistics (Bloomfield Fisher, 2019). A quantitative research design was suitable for studying the influence of socio-emotional competence on literacy progression as it allowed for precise measurement and analysis of the relationship between these variables. This approach provided statistically significant results that validated the extent to which socio-emotional skills impacted literacy skills. Quantifying this relationship enabled the creation of reliable, evidence-based recommendations for educational strategies and policies. Additionally, descriptive research methods were employed to describe the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied, without influencing the variables during the study. This method involved observing, recording, and describing the features of what was being studied (Dulock, 1993). Descriptive methods were appropriate for the initial phase of the study, where detailing the current state of socio-emotional competence and literacy levels among learners was essential. By accurately describing these aspects, researchers established a baseline understanding of the field and identified specific socio-emotional competencies that correlated with literacy outcomes. This foundational data was crucial for further exploration and hypothesis testing in later stages of research. Moreover,

the correlational research approach examined the relationship or association between two or more variables to determine if a statistically significant correlation existed. This method quantified the degree to which variables were related without implying a cause-and-effect relationship (Curtis et al., 2016). Using a correlational approach was ideal for exploring the relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression within the educational context. This method allowed researchers to identify patterns and strengths of associations between students' emotional and social skills and their literacy achievements. Insights gained from correlational analysis were valuable for educators and policymakers in designing interventions that fostered both socio-emotional and literacy development, effectively guiding resource allocation and program development.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher strictly followed the established protocols outlined in the standard guidelines for executing the research, paying close attention to the specified criteria for managing both the population and the data. The survey questionnaires, along with other related materials, were submitted for evaluation and approval. Upon receiving the green light from the RMC Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study.

Social Value The study on the influence of socio-emotional competence on literacy progression held considerable importance for the broader community. By identifying how teachers' social and emotional skills could enhance learners' reading and writing development, it contributed to improving overall educational outcomes. This improvement led to more con-

fidest learners who were better prepared for future academic and career paths. Additionally, strong literacy skills were associated with increased social and economic opportunities, benefiting both individuals and their communities. Hence, the study carried potential value not only for the schools in Sulop District but also for society at large. Moreover, this research highlighted the need to integrate socio-emotional learning into standard teaching practices. By showcasing the positive impact of socio-emotional competence on literacy, it encouraged educational stakeholders to prioritize teacher training in both academic and emotional domains. As a result, the capacity for holistic learner development grew, leading to a more inclusive and nurturing school environment. These advancements contributed to higher retention rates, better student performance, and more supportive relationships within the classroom. Thus, the findings inspired policy reforms and curriculum enhancements that uplifted the quality of education in the district. Additionally, the study's focus on public elementary school teachers in Sulop District ensured that its outcomes were directly relevant to the local educational context. The insights gained guided school administrators and policymakers in formulating strategies that addressed the unique social and emotional needs of teachers, who, in turn, supported their learners more effectively. In the long run, improving socio-emotional competence led to better literacy progression, fostering a culture of lifelong learning. This culture extended beyond the classroom, influencing families and communities to place greater value on education. Consequently, the social value of the research was evident in its capacity to promote sustained educational growth and well-being among learners. Informed Consent Securing informed consent was a crucial step in maintaining ethical research standards. The researcher clearly explained the purpose of the study to the respondent teachers, emphasizing how it aimed to ex-

plore the connection between socio-emotional competence and learners' literacy progression. Additionally, the teachers were informed about the potential benefits of this research, such as improvements in teaching strategies and learner outcomes. They were also made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any penalties. This transparent communication ensured that teachers fully understood their role and felt comfortable participating. Further, the researcher provided written consent forms that outlined the study's objectives, procedures, and the expected duration of participation. These forms detailed how the collected data would be used, stored, and protected to maintain confidentiality. Teachers had the chance to ask questions or express concerns before signing, ensuring they comprehended all aspects of their involvement. In this way, the researcher showed respect for the teachers' autonomy and acknowledged their professional responsibilities. This formal documentation confirmed that respondents agreed to participate voluntarily and with full knowledge of the study's parameters. Furthermore, the informed consent process emphasized the study's focus on ethical standards, including confidentiality and data protection. Teachers were reassured that their identities and personal information would remain anonymous in any reports or presentations resulting from the research. If any teacher decided to withdraw at any point, the researcher would remove any data associated with that individual. By respecting the teachers' decisions and ensuring their well-being, the research upheld principles of respect and integrity. In doing so, it fostered a supportive atmosphere and encouraged honest, unbiased feedback from respondents. Vulnerability of Research Respondents Public elementary school teachers could be considered vulnerable in this research context due to the potential pressure they might have felt when their teaching methods and socio-emotional skills were examined.

This pressure might have arisen from concerns about professional judgment or criticism, causing heightened anxiety or stress. To address this vulnerability, the researcher conducted the study in a respectful and non-threatening manner, clarifying that the goal was to improve educational practices, not to evaluate individual performance. The researcher also provided clear explanations about how the data would be kept confidential, ensuring that teachers understood their identities and specific classroom activities would remain private. By establishing trust and ensuring confidentiality, the study minimized undue stress among the respondent teachers. Additionally, the researcher remained sensitive to the teachers' busy schedules and work demands, acknowledging that their primary focus was on educating learners. Any data collection methods, such as surveys or interviews, were scheduled at times that were convenient for the teachers, thereby reducing potential disruptions to their teaching responsibilities. The researcher was also open to feedback or concerns from respondents about the research process. When challenges arose, the researcher adapted methods to ensure that the teachers' well-being remained a priority. This flexible and empathetic approach contributed to a respectful research environment, recognizing and alleviating the vulnerabilities of the respondent teachers. Privacy and Confidentiality Maintaining the privacy and confidentiality of respondents was paramount in this study, and the researcher strictly adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure that all personal information was handled with utmost care and security. Personal identifiers, such as names and school affiliations, and any other sensitive information were removed or coded to protect the identity of each respondent. This anonymization process ensured that individual responses could not be traced back to any specific teacher, thereby safeguarding their privacy throughout the research process. In addition to anonymizing data, the researcher im-

plemented secure data storage practices to protect both digital and physical copies of the data collected. Digital data was stored on password-protected devices and encrypted files, accessible only to the researcher and authorized personnel involved in the study. Physical copies, such as printed surveys or consent forms, were kept in locked cabinets in a secure location, inaccessible to unauthorized individuals. These measures ensured that all data remained confidential and protected against unauthorized access or breaches. Upon completing the study, the researcher ensured the proper disposal of all data in accordance with ethical guidelines and legal requirements. Soft copies of data were permanently deleted from all digital storage systems, while hard copies were shredded to prevent any possibility of data retrieval. This final step in data management underscored the researcher's commitment to upholding the highest standards of privacy and confidentiality, ensuring that the information provided by respondents remained protected even after the study concluded.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study involved a sample of 216 public elementary school teachers, selected from an estimated total of 470 public elementary school teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. This sample size was determined using the Slovin Formula, a statistical tool that helps ensure sufficient representation of the overall population. By applying this formula, the study aimed to achieve a balance between manageability and accuracy, reducing the margin of error. This approach allowed the researcher to gather insights that reasonably mirrored the experiences and perspectives of all teachers in the district. On the one hand, the stratified random sampling technique was used to choose the respondents. According to Ding et al. (1996), this method involved dividing the population into distinct groups, called strata, based on a common characteristic, then randomly selecting respondents from each stratum in proportion to their repre-

sentation in the total population. For this study, each public elementary school in Sulop District served as a stratum, ensuring that teachers from different schools were included. The researcher compiled a list of teachers in each school and randomly selected the appropriate number of respondents from each list. Through this process, the study achieved a fair and accurate representation of teachers across the entire district. To determine the final selection of respondents, the researcher established specific inclusion criteria. Only public elementary school teachers who were actively teaching full-time in Sulop District were included, ensuring that respondents had current, relevant classroom experience. Teachers with at least one year of teaching experience were prioritized to capture insights from individuals already familiar with the school environment. Adding more, only those who consented to participate and agreed to fulfill the study requirements were considered.

2.4. Research Instrument—The researcher utilized an adapted and modified survey questionnaire tailored to the current investigation. The scaling was performed by setting one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point, or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administering the instrument, it will be subjected to validation by three experts and revised according to their expert comments. The first part measured the socio-emotional competence of learners. This questionnaire consisted of 20 statements, divided among the following domains: emotional regulation, empathy, social initiation, and conflict resolution. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument was 0.820, described as very good, indicating a high reliability and internal consistency among the items. Responses will be collected using a 5-point Likert scale to assess the extent of agreement or disagreement with each statement, with subsequent analysis based on predefined ranges of means that were categorized to analyze the data effectively. The ranges of means are as follows:

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The socio-emotional competence of learners is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The socio-emotional competence of learners is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The socio-emotional competence of learners is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The socio-emotional competence of learners is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The socio-emotional competence of learners is never observed.

The second part of the instrument measured the literacy progression of learners. This questionnaire consists of 20 statements that were divided among the domains: reading accuracy, text comprehension, writing clarity and organization, and vocabulary usage. The Cronbach alpha value for this instrument was 0.945, described as excellent, indicating a high reliability and internal consistency among the items. The data collection utilized a 5-point Likert scale, allowing respondents to indicate their level of

agreement or disagreement with each statement. The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale, enabling respondents to indicate their level of agreement with each statement. The gathered responses were then analyzed using predefined mean ranges to systematically categorize the data, enabling the researchers to clearly define and interpret the intensity of respondents' perceptions towards the survey topics.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The literacy progression of learners is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The literacy progression of learners is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The literacy progression of learners is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The literacy progression of learners is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The literacy progression of learners is never evident.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher took several steps in conducting the study. These are as follows: Permission to Conduct the Study The first step in securing permission to conduct the study involved the researcher obtaining an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. This endorsement served as a formal recognition and support of the research project, validating its academic merit and alignment with the institution’s research objectives. Subsequently, the researcher applied for ethical clearance from the Graduate School RMC-Research Ethics Committee (GSRMC-REC). The ethical clearance was crucial as it ensured that the study adhered to established ethical standards, particularly in terms of confidentiality, consent, and the overall welfare of the respondents. Once the endorsement and ethical clearance were secured, the researcher approached the Schools Division Superintendent in Davao del Sur to request permission to conduct the study within the schools of Sulop District. This request included attaching copies of both the endorsement from the Dean and the ethical clearance certificate to demonstrate compliance with academic and ethical standards. Following approval from the superintendent, the researcher contacted the principals of the individual schools in Sulop District. During this phase, the researcher explained the study’s purpose, its potential benefits for the educational community, and the specific roles and expectations of the schools and their teachers, ensuring transparency and fostering cooperation. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire The first step in distributing the questionnaire involved selecting research respondents,

who were based on established inclusion criteria, ensuring that all respondents were elementary school teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. This was followed by a pilot test conducted on a small group of respondents to ensure the clarity and reliability of the questionnaire. The pilot test helped identify any ambiguities or biases in the questions, allowing the researcher to make necessary adjustments. This testing phase was crucial for validating the questionnaire’s effectiveness in accurately collecting the intended data. Following the successful pilot test, the main distribution of the research questionnaires occurred. The selected respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, ensuring they could provide thoughtful and thorough responses. Respondents had the flexibility to choose their preferred method of completion, either face-to-face or online, accommodating their convenience and comfort levels. This approach not only facilitated a higher response rate but also accommodated the diverse preferences and schedules of the respondents, potentially enhancing the quality and accuracy of the data collected. The final phase involved retrieving the completed questionnaires. The researcher established a deadline for submission, which was communicated clearly at the time of distribution. Respondents submitted their completed questionnaires through the predetermined method, either returning the physical documents in face-to-face settings or submitting them electronically. Once all questionnaires were collected, the researcher proceeded with data analysis, using statistical software to quantify the results and examine the influence of socio-emotional competence on the literacy pro-

gression among learners in public elementary schools. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data Upon retrieval of the completed survey questionnaires, the initial step involved tallying and organizing the data. Each response was systematically entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, categorized by various indicators, including socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners. This careful organization was crucial for ensuring that the subsequent analyses were based on accurate and systematically arranged data. The use of Excel also facilitated the sorting and filtering of data, allowing for an efficient preliminary examination and preparation for more complex statistical analysis. Following the organization of the data, the researcher conducted descriptive statistical analysis to derive initial insights into the collected data. This included calculating the mean for each variable to determine central tendencies. The mean provided a basic understanding of the average responses to various questions, indicating common trends and attitudes among the teachers regarding socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners. The final step in the data analysis involved conducting inferential statistical tests to explore the predictive relationships specified in the study's objectives. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used to identify the strength and direction of the relationships between variables, such as the correlation between

socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners. Regression analysis was then applied to determine the extent to which socio-emotional competence influenced the variations in literacy progression among learners. This inferential analysis not only validated the hypothesized relationships but also provided quantifiable evidence that could inform policy and practice within the educational sector.

2.6. Data Analysis—The researcher utilized the following statistical tools in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was used to measure the extent of socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners. This provides answers to SOP 1 and 2. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. In this study, this measures the strength and direction of the relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners. This correlation indicated whether higher empathy in leadership is associated with greater trust among teachers, showing either a positive correlation (where both increase together), a negative correlation (where one increases as the other decreases), or no correlation. This provided an answer to SOP 3. Regression Analysis. Regression analysis was used in this study to determine which domains of socio-emotional competence significantly influence literacy progression among learners. This statistical tool provided an answer to SOP 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools, the significant relationship between these variables, and the influence of socio-emotional competence on literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur.

3.1. Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners—

3.1.1. Emotional Regulation—Results in Table 1 indicate that socio-emotional competence, specifically in terms of emotional regu-

lation, among learners achieved a mean score of 3.44, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed. This indicates that a student’s ability to manage and respond to an emotional experience in a suitable manner is often observed. The result is consistent with Haun’s (2020) view that learners are capable of extensively regulating their emotions. Accordingly, learners who manage their emotions effectively remain more focused, resilient, and capable of overcoming learning challenges. Notably, the range of means on this particular domain was

3.34 to 3.55. The statement with the highest mean is Noticing students staying calm during challenging activities, which scored 3.55, described as extensive. In contrast, the statement with the lowest mean is Recognizing that students remain composed when receiving feedback, with a mean of 3.34, which falls into the moderately extensive range. Rezaei and Zebardest (2021) demonstrate that mindful emotional control helps students stay motivated and minimizes negative behaviors that hinder academic progress.

Table 1. Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners in Terms of Emotional Regulation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students staying calm during challenging activities.	3.55	Extensive
Observing learners managing their emotions after setbacks.	3.52	Extensive
Seeing peers controlling their anger in stressful situations.	3.42	Extensive
Recognizing that students remain composed when receiving feedback.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing fewer emotional outbursts during class.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.44	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

3.1.2. *Empathy*—As shown in Table 2, socio-emotional competence in terms of empathy got a mean score of 3.39, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The result means that the ability to understand and share the feelings, thoughts, and experiences of another person from their perspective is sometimes observed. The result is similar to the findings of Compton and Lindner (2025), who found that empathetic learners are more likely to engage in prosocial behaviors, such as helping and cooperating with others, which are important for collaborative learning activities. These students often exhibit a greater ability to navigate the social complexities of the classroom and school environment effectively. Notably, the range of means on this particu-

lar domain was 3.16 to 3.59. The statement Observing learners showing concern for classmates in need received the highest mean of 3.59, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. Conversely, the statement Recognizing that students listen carefully to others’ problems yielded the lowest mean of 3.16, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. Zaky (2024) revealed that learners with average empathy skills may exhibit inconsistent understanding of peer and teacher emotions, which can impact their ability to respond appropriately in social learning contexts. Such students may occasionally misinterpret social cues or fail to fully appreciate the perspectives of others, which can lead to misunderstandings or conflicts.

Table 2. Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners in Terms of Empathy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students understanding how others feel.	3.56	Extensive
Observing learners showing concern for classmates in need.	3.59	Extensive
Seeing peers offering help to those who are struggling.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing that students listen carefully to others' problems.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing increased kindness and support among classmates.	3.47	Extensive
Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

3.1.3. *Social Initiation*—The result in Table 3 shows that socio-emotional competence in terms of social initiation is 3.59, rated as extensive, described as oftentimes observed. This means that the learners' ability to start interactions or engage with others in social situations, such as beginning a conversation, asking questions, or joining group activities, was oftentimes observed. As noted by Kaseke and

Luvalo (2025), a high level of socio-emotional competence in social initiation significantly benefits teaching and learning processes. Those students are adept at initiating social interactions and contribute positively to a classroom's social climate, making it more conducive to active and engaging learning experiences. These students often bring energy and enthusiasm that can be contagious, positively affecting their peers' participation and interest in class activities.

Table 3. Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners in Terms of Social Initiation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students starting conversations with new classmates.	3.69	Extensive
Observing learners joining group activities willingly.	3.45	Extensive
Seeing peers introducing themselves to others in the class.	3.83	Extensive
Recognizing that students take the lead in organizing group work.	3.56	Extensive
Experiencing more students engaging in social interactions during breaks.	3.44	Extensive
Mean	3.59	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

Meanwhile, the range of means on this particular domain is 3.44 to 3.83. Among the statements, the highest mean was 3.83 for 'Seeing peers introducing themselves to others in the class,' which was described as 'extensive' at 3.44. Conversely, the lowest mean is for the

statement Experiencing more students engaging in social interactions during breaks which is also described as extensive. The result supports the view of Aal Ismail et al. (2022) that such learners are typically more successful in forming and maintaining friendships, a crucial aspect

of school adjustment and emotional well-being. These students are often perceived as leaders and can positively influence group dynamics, thereby facilitating collaborative learning. Enhanced social initiation skills allow learners to feel more connected and secure within their social groups, fostering a supportive network that can enhance their educational experience.

3.1.4. Conflict Resolution—The mean score of 3.30, categorized as moderately extensive, indicates that the learners’ socio-emotional competence in terms of conflict resolution was observed sometimes within the classroom setting. This means that the ability to negotiate and constructively resolve disagreements is sometimes observed among the respondents. This aligns with the notion of Morozova et al. (2022) that students with moderate skills in conflict resolution may occasionally struggle with disputes, which can interrupt classroom activities and negatively impact the learning environment. However, these same students often possess enough

foundational skills to benefit from targeted instructional interventions, such as conflict resolution training or peer mediation programs. Moreover, the range of means on this particular domain was 3.19 to 3.42. The highest mean score of 3.42 is for the statement Noticing students finding solutions during disagreements which was described as extensive. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.19 is for the statement Experiencing fewer unresolved disputes in the classroom which belongs to a moderately extensive descriptive rating. As proposed by Hatun and Serin (2021), integrating conflict resolution training within the curriculum can enhance learners’ ability to handle conflicts independently, reducing the need for teacher intervention and allowing more time for instructional activities. When students learn to manage disputes effectively, it fosters a more supportive and collaborative classroom atmosphere, enhancing the overall learning experience.

Table 4. Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners in Terms of Conflict Resolution

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students finding solutions during disagreements.	3.42	Extensive
Observing learners mediating conflicts between classmates.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Seeing peers using words to resolve issues instead of fighting.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing that students seek compromise during conflicts.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing fewer unresolved disputes in the classroom.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.30	Moderately Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

Lastly, results in Table 5 show that socio-emotional competence among learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, acquired a mean score of 3.43, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. The result was consistent with the findings of Rocha et al. (2024), who reported that

students with moderate socio-emotional skills may exhibit inconsistent behavior in their emotional regulation and social interactions, which can impact classroom dynamics and the effectiveness of collaborative learning efforts. These learners might show adequate skills in familiar, structured settings but struggle in more dynamic

or socially demanding situations. On one hand, socio-emotional competence in terms of social initiation stands out with the highest mean score of 3.59, which was described as extensive. On the other end, socio-emotional competence in terms of conflict resolution records the lowest mean of 3.30, falling into the moderately extensive descriptive rating. As noted by Knigge et al. (2019), these competencies were crucial

for navigating social interactions and enhancing personal development effectively. Accordingly, learners with extensive socio-emotional skills tend to have better school adjustment and improved academic performance. These skills allow learners to manage stress and provide the tools to engage constructively in conflict situations.

Table 5. Summary on Socio-Emotional Competence among Learners in Public Elementary Schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Emotional Regulation	3.44	Extensive
Empathy	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Social Initiation	3.59	Extensive
Conflict Resolution	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.43	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

3.2. Literacy Progression among Learners—

3.2.1. *Reading Accuracy*—Literacy progression among learners in terms of reading accuracy was 3.47, described as Extensive, meaning it was oftentimes evident in classroom observations. The result means that the ability of the students to pronounce words and read text without errors correctly was oftentimes evident. The result supports the view of Shin and McMaster (2019) that oral reading and maze assessments correlated moderately with students’ comprehension, suggesting that incremental improvements in reading accuracy positively influence understanding. The range of means on this par-

ticular domain is 3.32 to 3.57. The statement “Recognizing that students follow along accurately during group reading” has a mean of 3.57, described as extensive. Conversely, the statement “Noticing students reading aloud without frequent mistakes” recorded the lowest mean score of 3.32, described as moderately extensive. According to Makebo et al. (2022), moderate improvements in reading accuracy can help students strengthen their literacy skills. Moreover, as reading fluency increases, comprehension also rises at a moderate rate. Consequently, ensuring balanced and steady growth in reading accuracy fosters more effective literacy outcomes.

3.2.2. *Text Comprehension*—The result in Table 7 shows that literacy progression among learners, in terms of text comprehension, yielded a mean score of 3.37, which is classified as moderately extensive and interpreted as

sometimes evident among the respondents. This indicates that students’ ability to understand and interpret the meaning behind words and phrases within a specific context is sometimes evident in the classroom setting. The result aligns with the

Table 6. Literacy Progression among Learners in Terms of Reading Accuracy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students reading aloud without frequent mistakes.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners correctly pronouncing difficult words.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Seeing peers reading smoothly with little hesitation.	3.54	Extensive
Recognizing that students follow along accurately during group reading.	3.57	Extensive
Experiencing fewer students struggling with basic phonics.	3.56	Extensive
Mean	3.47	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

idea of Bogaerds-Hazenberget al. (2021) that learners with moderate comprehension skills may grasp literal information but often struggle with the inferential and evaluative aspects of texts. This limitation can hinder their ability to fully engage with more complex materials and discussions, impacting their overall academic performance.

Table 7. Literacy Progression among Learners in Terms of Text Comprehension

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students answering questions correctly after reading a passage.	3.54	Extensive
Observing learners discussing the main ideas of the text accurately.	3.44	Extensive
Seeing peers connecting the text to their own experiences.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing that students can predict outcomes based on earlier parts of the text.	3.50	Extensive
Experiencing learners asking insightful questions that show deep understanding.	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.37	Moderately Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

Meanwhile, the range of means on this particular domain is 3.17 to 3.54. The highest mean score of 3.54, or extensive, was observed on the statement Noticing students answering questions correctly after reading a passage. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.17, indicating a moderately extensive level, was for the statement 'Experiencing learners asking insightful questions that show deep understanding.' According to Shanniyah (2019), skilled comprehension enables students to engage with a variety of texts, facilitating deeper learning and the development of critical thinking skills. Effective text comprehension also supports the ability to summarize content, infer meanings beyond the text, and evaluate arguments, which are essential skills for academic and lifelong learning.

3.2.3. *Writing Clarity and Organization*— The mean score of 3.50 for literacy progression among learners in terms of writing clarity and

organization falls within the extensive category, interpreted as oftentimes evident in the classroom. The result means that students' ability to express thoughts in a clear, logical, and coherent manner through writing was oftentimes evident. This aligns with the assertion by Li and Huang (2022) that students who excel in organizing their thoughts and articulating them clearly tend to perform better in essay assignments and exams, which are standard assessment methods in many educational settings. These skills enable learners to effectively convey their knowledge and arguments, which are critical for academic success and progression. The range of means of this particular domain is 3.33 to 3.58. The high-

est mean score of 3.58 is for the statement Noticing students writing paragraphs with clear main ideas, described as oftentimes evident. Conversely, the statement Seeing peers organizing their essays in a logical sequence scored the lowest mean of 3.33, categorized as moderately extensive. Eck (2022) emphasized that achieving writing clarity and organization significantly enhances students' literacy progression. By focusing on clear structure and concise expression, students can communicate their ideas more effectively. As a result, improved writing skills lead to higher academic performance and better overall literacy outcomes.

Table 8. Literacy Progression among Learners in Terms of Writing Clarity and Organization

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students writing paragraphs with clear main ideas.	3.58	Extensive
Observing learners using appropriate transitions between thoughts.	3.56	Extensive
Seeing peers organizing their essays in a logical sequence.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing that students consistently adhere to topic sentences.	3.51	Extensive
Experiencing fewer students expressing confusion about how to structure their writing.	3.53	Extensive
Mean	3.50	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

3.2.4. *Vocabulary Usage*—The mean score for literacy progression in terms of vocabulary usage among learners is 3.26, falling into the moderately extensive category. This means that the ability and frequency with which students use a diverse and appropriate vocabulary in both spoken and written forms were sometimes evident. Lee et al. (2019) noted that a moderate level of literacy progression in vocabulary usage can have a significant impact on teaching and learning processes. Students with only a moderate vocabulary range may struggle with text comprehension and the abil-

ity to express complex ideas, which can hinder their learning in content-rich subjects such as science and social studies. The range of means for this particular domain is 2.98 to 3.51. The highest mean score of 3.51 is for the statement Noticing students using new vocabulary words correctly in sentences, described as extensive. Conversely, the lowest mean of 2.98 is for the statement Recognizing that students understand the meanings of words they use, which was described as moderately extensive. Ketola (2019) highlighted that students with a wide range of vocabulary can express their thoughts more

precisely and persuasively in writing and oral discussions. Effective vocabulary usage is not only about the number of words known but also about how effectively students use these words in context, which enhances their overall academic and social communication.

Table 9. Literacy Progression among Learners in Terms of Vocabulary Usage

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students using new vocabulary words correctly in sentences.	3.51	Extensive
Observing learners applying specialized terms relevant to different subjects.	3.14	Extensive
Seeing peers experimenting with synonyms to express their ideas.	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing that students understand the meanings of words they use.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing an increase in the variety of words used by students in their writing.	3.48	Extensive
Mean	3.26	Moderately Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

Lastly, literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools had a mean score of 3.40, classified under extensive descriptive rating and interpreted as oftentimes evident. This indicates that the ongoing development and enhancement of skills necessary to decode, comprehend, and produce both spoken and written language was oftentimes evident among the learners in public elementary school in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. This supports the view of Abbas et al. (2019) that a high level of literacy progression is crucial in the teaching-learning processes as it forms the backbone of effective educational engagement. Advanced literacy skills enable learners to comprehend complex texts, engage in higher-order thinking, and participate more fully in academic discussions. These capabilities are essential for

meeting the rigorous demands of contemporary curricula across educational levels. Among the domains, the highest mean score is found in writing clarity and organization, at 3.51, which is described as extensive. On the other end of the spectrum, vocabulary usage scores the lowest with a mean of 3.26, falling into the moderately extensive category. Cameron et al. (2020) noted that as learners progress in their literacy skills, they demonstrate improved comprehension, greater ability to analyze and synthesize information, and enhanced capacity to express themselves in both written and verbal forms. Effective literacy development supports not only academic achievement but also critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for lifelong learning and adaptation to diverse life contexts.

3.3. *Socio-Emotional Competence and Literacy Progression among Learners in Public Elementary Schools*—The results of the analysis on the relationship between socio-emotional

competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, were presented. Bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson

Table 10. Summary on Literacy Progression among Learners in Public Elementary Schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Reading Accuracy	3.47	Extensive
Text Comprehension	3.42	Extensive
Writing Clarity and Organization	3.51	Extensive
Vocabulary Usage	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.40	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

Product-Moment Correlation, was employed to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows that socio-emotional competence has a significant positive relationship with literacy progression among learners, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.711$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of socio-emotional competence changes, literacy progression among learners also changes significantly. The result indicates that students who demonstrate stronger socio-emotional skills, such as self-regulation and empathy, tend to have better literacy outcomes. This suggests that enhancing socio-emotional learning in educational settings can significantly improve students' reading and writing abilities, contributing to their overall academic success. This supports the findings of Turner-Moore (2022), who argued that socio-emotional skills such as self-regulation and empathy are linked to higher levels of engagement and comprehension in reading tasks. These competencies enable learners to understand characters' emotions and motivations more effectively within texts, thereby enhancing their ability to make inferences and connect concepts. Moreover, the results in the table indicate that socio-emotional

competence, as measured by emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution, was significantly correlated with literacy progression among learners, as evidenced by the correlation coefficient values of 0.531, 0.363, and 0.637, respectively. Thus, this led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. The result means that students who excel in areas such as emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution tend to achieve higher proficiency in reading and writing skills. This finding aligns with the view of Batini et al. (2021), who suggest that students who can effectively manage their emotions are more likely to exhibit persistence and resilience when faced with challenging reading materials or complex literacy tasks. This persistence was crucial for developing deeper literacy skills and broader academic success. Additionally, Aleksić et al. (2019) noted that students skilled in socio-emotional competencies tend to contribute more constructively to discussions and are better equipped to take advantage of collaborative learning opportunities.

3.4. *Influence of Socio-Emotional Competence on the Literacy Progression among Learn-*

ers in Public Elementary Schools—The influence of socio-emotional competence on literacy

Table 11. Relationship Between Socio-Emotional Competence and Literacy Progression among Learners in Public Elementary Schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Socio-Emotional Competence	r-value	p-value	Decision
Emotional Regulation	0.531*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Empathy	0.363*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Social Initiation	0.125	0.067	Accept H ₀
Conflict Resolution	0.637*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Overall Socio-Emotional Competence	0.711*	0.000	Reject H ₀

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$.

progression among learners in public elementary schools yields significant insights, as evidenced by the regression analysis results presented in the table. In a singular capacity, socio-emotional competence, specifically emotional regulation, significantly influenced literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools, with a p-value of less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) ($p < .05$) and a positive standardized beta value of .290. It means that for every unit increase in the value of socio-emotional competence in terms of emotional regulation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.290 in the extent of literacy progression among learners. The result implies that students who are better at managing their emotions tend to achieve higher literacy skills. This suggests that interventions aimed at improving emotional regulation could be a strategic focus to enhance reading and writing capabilities, thereby supporting broader educational outcomes. This aligns with the view of Yu et al. (2023) that, through a meta-analysis, emotional regulation and other social-emotional skills are closely linked to reading abilities in typically developing readers. Their findings indicate that students with strong emotional control display higher motivation, engagement, and persistence

in literacy activities. The studies suggest that emotional regulation creates a calm and focused learning environment, supporting continuous growth in students' reading skills and overall literacy development. Furthermore, in a singular capacity, socio-emotional competence, specifically empathy, significantly influenced literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools, with a p-value of less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($p < .05$) and a positive beta value of 0.124. It means that for every unit increase in the extent of socio-emotional competence in terms of empathy, there is a corresponding increase of .124 in the extent of literacy progression among learners. This means that students who can understand and share the feelings of others are better equipped to engage with and comprehend texts. The result aligns with Patel's (2023) findings, which suggest that empathy enables students to engage more fully with reading materials by placing themselves in the context of the story or the emotions of the characters, thereby making reading a more personal and meaningful experience. Therefore, fostering empathy not only aids in academic literacy but also enriches students' overall educational journey, making them more receptive and connected learners.

Table 12. Influence of Socio-Emotional Competence on the Literacy Progression among Learners in Public Elementary Schools

Socio-Emotional Competence	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Emotional Regulation	.290**	.387	.034	.000	Reject H ₀
Empathy	.124**	.181	.031	.000	Reject H ₀
Social Initiation	-.012	-.015	.034	.727	Accept H ₀
Conflict Resolution	.286**	.527	.024	.000	Reject H ₀
Adjusted R²	= 0.598				
F-value	= 80.843**				
p-value	= 0.000				

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Legend: H₀ = Null Hypothesis; B = Unstandardized Coefficient; Beta = Standardized Coefficient; S.E. = Standard Error.

Furthermore, in a singular capacity, socio-emotional competence in terms of conflict resolution significantly influenced literacy progression among learners in public elementary schools, with a p-value of less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($p < .05$) and a positive beta value of .286. It means that for every unit increase in the extent of socio-emotional competence in terms of conflict resolution, there was a corresponding increase of .286 in the extent of literacy progression among learners. This suggests that incorporating conflict resolution training into educational programs could significantly enhance literacy development by improving students' abilities to articulate their thoughts and comprehend complex narratives in academic settings. This was consistent with Camacho Ortiz's (2020) view that students proficient in conflict resolution are more likely to participate actively in classroom discussions and literary circles without being disrupted by interpersonal conflicts. This active participation enables them to engage more deeply with texts, enhancing their comprehension and analytical skills. Lastly, the adjusted R-squared value of 0.598 indicates that approximately 60 % of the variance in literacy progression can be explained by the socio-emotional competence variables included in the model. This substantial figure suggests a

strong relationship between these competencies and literacy outcomes. The F-value of 80.843, with a p-value of 0.000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) ($p < 0.05$), further confirms the statistical significance of the overall model, indicating that the set of socio-emotional competencies significantly predicts literacy progression, far beyond what could be expected by chance alone. In conducting this research, it is crucial to evaluate the extent to which the empirical data corroborate or contradict the underlying theoretical assumptions. As regards Emotional Intelligence Theory by Goleman (1995), this suggests that by developing emotional intelligence, learners can create a more positive and focused environment for reading and comprehension. Emotional skills, such as empathy and self-regulation, support cooperative learning, which can enhance literacy progression. Furthermore, Self-Determination Theory, as proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985), posits that fostering intrinsic motivation through the development of socio-emotional competencies increases the likelihood of students engaging actively with reading materials. Supporting students' needs for autonomy and competence can lead to a more motivated and confident approach to learning the English language.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion was supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion was in accordance with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of socio-emotional competence significantly influenced literacy progression among learners, utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 216 Public Elementary School teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, as respondents using a stratified random sampling method. The researcher utilized modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument's items. First, socio-emotional competence observed among learners was extensive, with students frequently demonstrating strengths in managing their emotions and initiating social interactions. Empathy and conflict resolution were moderately extensive, indicating that these competencies were somewhat less consistently exhibited compared to emotional regulation and social initiation. These findings suggest that while students generally displayed robust socio-emotional skills, there is potential for enhanced development in fostering deeper empathy and more effective conflict resolution strategies. Second, literacy progression among learners was extensive, indicating that most literacy skills were frequently observed. Reading accuracy, text comprehension, and writing clarity and organization were notably extensive, while vocabulary usage was moderately extensive. These findings suggest that although learners exhibit strong capabilities in core literacy areas, further enhancement of vocabulary usage may foster even more comprehensive literacy development. Third, the findings revealed that overall socio-emotional competence was sig-

nificantly associated with literacy progression among learners, indicating that stronger socio-emotional skills tend to correspond with higher literacy outcomes. Key dimensions such as emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution demonstrated notable positive relationships with literacy, while social initiation did not show a significant correlation. These results imply that enhancing targeted socio-emotional skills could contribute to improved literacy development in elementary education within the district. Lastly, the findings indicated that emotional regulation and empathy positively influenced literacy progression among learners, underscoring the critical role of these socio-emotional skills in enhancing academic achievement. In contrast, social initiation did not significantly predict literacy progression, while conflict resolution demonstrated a meaningful contribution to advancing learners' literacy outcomes. Overall, the socio-emotional competencies examined in the study accounted for a substantial portion of the variation in literacy progression, highlighting the importance of developing these skills to support and improve educational performance in public elementary schools.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: It was concluded that the socio-emotional competence among learners was extensive, indicating that these skills were frequently demonstrated in the school environment. In particular, students exhibited higher levels of emotional regulation and social initiation, while their empathy and conflict resolution skills were somewhat less pronounced, suggesting specific areas for further development. These conclusions suggest that targeted interventions to enhance

empathy and conflict resolution may lead to more balanced socio-emotional development, ultimately fostering a more supportive and effective learning environment. Moreover, the literacy progression among learners was extensive, as evidenced by strong performance in reading accuracy, text comprehension, and writing clarity and organization. Vocabulary usage, while positive, was observed at a moderately extensive level, suggesting that targeted strategies could further enhance lexical development. Consequently, implementing instructional approaches that integrate vocabulary enrichment with existing literacy practices may optimize literacy progression and support improved academic performance. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that overall socio-emotional competence had a significant influence on literacy progression, indicating that higher levels of emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution were associated with improved literacy outcomes among the learners. In contrast, social initiation did not show a significant relationship with literacy progression, suggesting that not all socio-emotional skills equally affect academic performance. These findings suggest that targeted interventions designed to enhance specific socio-emotional competencies may be an effective strategy for promoting better literacy development in public elementary schools. Furthermore, the findings indicated that aspects of socio-emotional competence, particularly Emotional Regulation, Empathy, and Conflict Resolution, significantly influenced literacy progression among learners, underscoring their pivotal role in fostering academic development. In contrast, Social Initiation did not exhibit a significant influence, suggesting that not all socio-emotional skills equally contribute to literacy outcomes. These results imply that interventions aimed at enhancing literacy should prioritize the development of Emotional Regulation, Empathy, and Conflict Resolution skills to support improved academic performance in

public elementary schools.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: For DepEd. The Department of Education (DepEd) should prioritize the integration of socio-emotional competency training within the national curriculum to support literacy progression among learners. Furthermore, it is recommended that policy frameworks be revised to incorporate evidence-based practices that foster emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution as key components of academic success. Additionally, DepEd could develop and disseminate professional development modules that emphasize the linkage between socio-emotional competence and literacy outcomes. Finally, collaborative initiatives between curriculum developers and academic researchers should be established to ensure that new strategies are both innovative and empirically validated. For School Heads. School heads are encouraged to create a supportive learning environment that emphasizes the development of socio-emotional skills alongside literacy instruction. They should facilitate targeted intervention programs that specifically enhance skills such as emotional regulation and conflict resolution, which have proven influential in literacy progression. Moreover, school heads can promote collaborative professional development sessions to disseminate best practices and innovative pedagogical approaches among teachers. Additionally, they should continually monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of these programs to ensure that they contribute to improved academic outcomes. For Elementary School Teachers. Elementary school teachers should integrate socio-emotional learning (SEL) strategies into daily classroom routines to enhance literacy skills among students. They are advised to use differentiated instruction methods that focus on developing critical socio-emotional competencies, such as empathy and emotional

regulation, which directly support literacy progression. Furthermore, teachers should employ reflective practices and formative assessments to monitor students' social and academic development, thereby adjusting their instructional strategies as needed. Additionally, collaborating with peers in professional learning communities can further enhance the implementation of integrated SEL and literacy initiatives. For Learners. Learners are encouraged to actively participate in activities that strengthen both their socio-emotional skills and literacy abilities, recognizing that these competencies mutually reinforce academic success. They should seek opportunities to engage in group projects, discussions, and reflective practices that promote emotional awareness and constructive conflict resolution. Moreover, learners must be encouraged to use literacy activities, such as reading and writing exercises, as platforms to effectively express and regulate their emotions. Additionally, students should be motivated to explore various learning resources and participate in programs that integrate socio-emotional learning with literacy development. For Future Researchers. Future researchers should further investigate the dynamic interplay between socio-emotional competence and literacy progression in diverse educational contexts, as these relationships remain crucial for academic achievement. They are encouraged to employ rigorous, longitudinal research designs that capture the evolution of these competencies over time. Additionally, exploring the moderating effects of contextual and cultural factors on these relationships would provide more nuanced insights into the effectiveness of educational interventions. Moreover, collaborative research efforts with educational institutions and policymakers are recommended to translate empirical findings into effective, scalable educational practices.

5. References

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